

Explanatory Sequential Study on the Relationship Between Alternative Delivery Modes and Learner Engagement: A Correlational Mixed-Methods Approach

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Abstract. This explanatory sequential mixed-methods study investigated the extent of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) implementation and its relationship with learner engagement in selected basic education contexts. Quantitative data were collected from 141 respondents through a structured survey and analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and linear regression. Results revealed that ADM implementation—comprising online, blended, modular, face-to-face learning and hybrid learning—was perceived to be moderately extensive, with face-to-face and modular modes rated highest. Learner engagement, however, was found to be less extensive in terms of participation and interaction, though moderately extensive in focus and collaboration. Statistical analysis showed no significant relationship between ADM implementation and learner engagement ($r = 0.153$, $p > .05$), and none of the ADM types significantly predicted engagement. Qualitative data, gathered through guided interviews, revealed that participants perceive ADM as a flexible but imperfect tool. Learner engagement was viewed as highly dependent on contextual factors such as technological access, home environment, and teacher-student interaction. The findings suggest that while ADM is essential for learning continuity, engagement depends more on instructional quality and support systems than on the delivery mode itself.

KEY WORDS

1. Alternative delivery mode 2. learner engagement 3. online learning

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1. Introduction

The relationship between alternative delivery modes and learner engagement is highly relevant in today's educational landscape, particularly as schools adapt to challenges such as limited resources, geographical barriers, and unforeseen disruptions like pandemics. The study investigates the influence of alternative instructional approaches including online, blended, modular, and media-assisted modalities on student engagement, which is recognized as a critical element of academic achievement. The findings aim to provide meaningful insights for educators, school administrators, and policymakers in refining educational strategies to promote equitable, inclusive, and effective learning experiences for all students, irrespective of their socio-economic or contextual limitations. This research holds significant social value by contributing to the development of flexible, equitable, and innovative learning solu-

tions for diverse learners. At the international level, the implementation of alternative delivery modes (ADMs) in teaching and learning has highlighted several key challenges that affect learner engagement. One of the primary issues is digital inequality. In many regions, students lack access to reliable internet, devices, or digital literacy skills necessary for participating in online or blended learning environments. This digital divide exacerbates disparities in education, particularly in rural or low-income areas, where students may struggle to access the same resources as their urban counterparts. As a result, learners' engagement is hindered as they face difficulties in accessing course materials, interacting with peers and instructors, and fully participating in online learning activities (Trifirò, et al., 2021). A key concern is the quality of content and instructional design in alternative delivery modes. Daugherty (2023) shared that while technology provides flexible learning opportunities, it also presents challenges in making materials engaging and pedagogically sound. Without proper educator training, transitioning to online or modular learning can result in poorly designed courses that fail to engage students. Many teachers are still adjusting to new technologies, struggling to integrate them effectively, which leads to passive learning experiences. This lack of engaging content can lower learner motivation and participation, hindering the effectiveness of ADMs in promoting active learning. Wu, et al., (2024) said that social isolation and limited interaction in alternative delivery modes hinder learners' emotional and behavioral engagement. In traditional classrooms, students gain motivation from. They may feel isolated and unsupported, leading to disengagement—particularly for younger learners who thrive on collaboration. The absence of real-time feedback and face-to-face connection further diminishes their emotional engagement, impacting motivation and material connection. This highlights the necessity for inclusive, supportive learning designs that cater to learners' social and emotional needs in alternative delivery modes. In the Philippine context, the learning has brought several pressing concerns that significantly affect learner engagement. One of the most notable challenges is the digital divide, particularly in remote and rural areas. Despite efforts to enhance access to technology, a large number of students still lack the necessary devices, reliable internet connections, and digital literacy skills (Villanueva, et al., 2022). These issues create substantial barriers to online learning, preventing students from fully participating in lessons, completing assignments, or engaging in virtual discussions. As a result, learners in underprivileged areas experience a disconnect from the educational process, which severely hampers their engagement and academic progress. Another significant concern is the limited teacher capacity and training in delivering content through alternative modes. While the shift to online, modular, or blended learning was necessary, many teachers were not adequately prepared for such a drastic change in pedagogy. Even though the Department of Education (DepEd) initiated training programs, many teachers still face challenges in effectively using digital platforms or designing engaging content for ADM. This teacher preparedness gap impacts instruction quality, leading to passive learning environments where students struggle to remain engaged. Additionally, teachers often face difficulties in providing personalized support to students, making it harder to maintain motivation and engagement, especially among those who require extra assistance (Lucero, 2020). Moreover, the quality and accessibility of learning materials in ADM remain critical concerns. In the case of modular learning, some students have reported receiving outdated, poorly designed, or difficult-to-understand materials, which contribute to frustration and disengagement. The quality of printed modules varies significantly

between schools and regions, and in some cases, teachers and students lack instructional support. In online and blended learning, the challenge lies in creating content that is not only accessible but also engaging and interactive. Without proper resources or sufficient guidance on how to navigate digital platforms, learners may disengage from the learning process, especially when faced with content that lacks interactivity or fails to hold their interest (Hermosisima, et al., 2023). In Davao City, especially in the General Roxas District, implementing alternative delivery modes (ADM) presents distinct challenges and opportunities. This district encompasses both urban and rural regions, each with different levels of technology access that greatly influence ADM's effectiveness. Urban areas generally benefit from improved internet connectivity and digital devices, while rural sections of General Roxas still face obstacles in accessing reliable internet and modern educational technologies. Furthermore, many learners resort to modular learning, which, while available, often struggles with the quality of educational materials and the capacity of teachers to provide timely feedback. The region's varied geographical features also influence the distribution of learning materials, frequently necessitating more effort to ensure adequate support for all students. This situation underscores the importance of developing tailored and context-sensitive solutions to maintain consistent student engagement.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—The theory of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) is based on the notion that education should be flexible and adaptable to accommodate the varied needs of learners, particularly in situations where conventional face-to-face instruction is not possible. ADM includes different instructional approaches. Various educational methodologies include online learning, blended learning, modular learning, and media-based learning (like television or ra-

dio), all aimed at providing accessible, scalable, and inclusive educational opportunities (Kipp et al., 2023). The theory asserts that learning should extend beyond traditional classroom settings, using technology and alternative media to cater to diverse learning styles, preferences, and situations. A key aspect of this theory is the belief that ADM should be structured to uphold or improve learner engagement, ensuring students remain cognitively, emotionally, and behaviorally active in their learning journey (Orlaniuk-Malitskaia, et al., 2024). It integrates principles from constructivism, which supports active, learner-centered experiences, and connectivism, emphasizing the significance of networking, interaction, and collaboration in education. By utilizing diverse learning modalities, ADM provides a more personalized learning experience, empowering students with the ability and flexibility to engage with content in ways that suit their individual needs while fostering a sense of community and social presence even in non-traditional educational settings. The conceptual framework on the relationship between Alternative Delivery Modes (ADM) and learner engagement, focusing on the variables of participation, interaction, and focus, posits that the design and structure of ADMs significantly affect students' engagement with learning process. The framework suggests that participation is influenced by the level of interactivity and the type of tasks provided in each delivery mode. In online and blended learning environments, participation is often higher when learners have opportunities for active involvement through discussions, assignments, and group activities. In contrast, modular learning may require more self-discipline to maintain consistent participation. Interaction is crucial in fostering deeper engagement, enabling students to connect with their peers, instructors, and course material. In ADM settings, interaction can occur in various forms, such as synchronous sessions, discussion forums, or collaborative projects, with the

framework emphasizing that stronger interactions lead to enhanced social presence and an improved sense of community. Focus is an essential component of engagement, as students must be able to maintain their attention on the learning material. The framework highlights that Alternative Delivery Modes that include clear learning objectives, interactive content, and regular feedback help sustain student focus, whereas poorly designed Alternative Delivery Modes may lead to distraction and disengagement.

2. Methodology

This study employs a mixed-methods approach to explore how alternative delivery modes (ADM) affect learner engagement, focusing on participation, interaction, and focus. It combines quantitative methods, using surveys to collect data on student engagement across various ADM environments like online, blended, and modular learning. Statistical analysis, including latent profile analysis, will identify patterns between ADM and engagement. The qualitative component consists of interviews, focus groups, and classroom observations to gain insights into experiences with ADM. Thematic analysis will reveal how engagement is fostered or hindered in different settings. By integrating these methods, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing learner engagement and offer actionable recommendations for improving ADM.

2.1. Research Design—This study utilized a mixed-methods approach, specifically following an explanatory sequential design. This two-phase methodology begins with the collection and analysis of quantitative data—often through tools like surveys or tests—to identify patterns or relationships among variables. The second phase involves qualitative data gathering, such as interviews or focus groups, to provide deeper insights and explanations for the initial quantitative results. This approach enables a more comprehensive understanding by combining numerical trends with contextual interpretation (Creswell Creswell, 2023). The qualitative phase enriches the study by offering in-depth insights and contextual understanding that quantitative data alone may not reveal. In a sequential design, this phase builds on the quantitative findings, allowing the researcher to explore underlying meanings and explanations more thoroughly (Given, 2008, as cited in Creswell Creswell, 2023). In mixed-methods research design, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches provides a more holistic view of the research problem by integrating numerical data with detailed personal or contextual insights. The quantitative phase is typically the first step, in which the researcher collects structured data, often using instruments such as surveys, tests, or questionnaires. This phase is focused on measuring and quantifying the extent of certain phenomena, looking for patterns, relationships, or statistical differences between variables. Once the quantitative analysis is complete, the researcher transitions to the qualitative phase, where non-numerical data is gathered through methods like interviews, focus groups, or observations (Creswell, J.W. and Creswell J. D., 2023). The qualitative phase builds upon the quantitative findings by offering deeper insights into the experiences, perspectives, and meanings behind the numbers. The quantitative phase reveals a strong correlation between two variables, and the qualitative phase might explore the reasons behind this relationship, seeking to understand the personal experiences or contextual factors that influence the observed trends. This method allows researchers to triangulate their data by

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

integrating the generalizability of quantitative methods with the detailed insights of qualitative methods. By employing both approaches, the researcher can develop a deeper and more intricate understanding of the research issue, providing more robust evidence and enhanced validity to the findings (Creswell, J. W. and Poth, C. N., 2016 as cited by Creswell, J.W. and Creswell J. D., 2023). The descriptive-correlational approach is a research design aimed at examining and illustrating the relationships among variables without altering them. Researchers use this method to observe and record a population or phenomenon's natural traits or behaviors. This method employs techniques such as surveys, questionnaires, or observations to gather insights about the participants. The correlational aspect of this approach focuses on analyzing the relationships among two or more variables. Rather than determining cause-and-effect links, the aim is to see if a relationship exists and measure the extent of that relationship. Although the descriptive-correlational method can reveal patterns or relationships, it falls short of proving causality. Correlational research design represents a category of research methodology employed to investigate the relationships or associations among two or more variables. The fundamental principle underlying this design is to ascertain whether a modification in one variable correlates with a modification in another, alongside evaluating the strength and direction of the relationship. Correlational research refrains from manipulating or controlling variables. Rather, it merely observes how variables manifest naturally within a specified context and evaluates their interrelation (Creswell, J.W. and Creswell J. D., 2023). Correlational research typically utilizes statistical methods such as Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) to assess the strength of relationships between variables, which can vary from -1 (representing a perfect negative correlation) to +1 (representing a perfect positive correlation), with 0 denoting no

correlation. It is imperative to recognize that, although correlations underscore associations, they do not establish causality. A significant drawback of correlational research is its inability to prove that one variable influences changes in another; it merely uncovers patterns or relationships. In this study on the relationship between alternative delivery modes (ADM) and learner engagement, the explanatory sequential mixed-methods design was applied. The quantitative phase employs correlational analysis to examine the statistical relationships between different ADM (such as online, blended, and modular learning) and key dimensions of learner engagement, including participation, interaction, and focus. This phase involves collecting numerical data through surveys or assessments that measure student engagement and then analyzing these data to determine patterns and correlations. The qualitative phase, using a phenomenological approach, seeks to provide a deeper understanding of how students experience engagement in ADM contexts. Through interviews, focus groups, or classroom observations, this phase explores the lived experiences of students and teachers, offering insights into the personal, social, and contextual factors that influence engagement. The combination of correlational analysis and phenomenological methods allows for a comprehensive exploration of both the broad patterns in learner engagement across different ADM and the in-depth, subjective experiences of participants, enriching the overall understanding of how ADM impact engagement in diverse learning environments.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—The ethical consideration section of this study addressed the key principles that ensure the protection and well-being of the teacher-respondents involved. This includes adhering to confidentiality, obtaining informed consent, and ensuring the voluntary nature of participation, thereby ensuring that the research is conducted with integrity and respect for the rights of all respondents.

Social Value.

This study's social value stems from its ability to enhance educational equity and accessibility by analyzing the effects of alternative delivery modes (ADM) on learner engagement. As education increasingly moves beyond traditional classroom settings, especially in response to challenges like geographical isolation and crises, understanding how to engage learners in diverse environments is crucial. This study provides valuable insights to assist educators and policymakers in creating more inclusive, adaptable, and engaging learning experiences, guaranteeing that every student, irrespective of their circumstances, has equal opportunities for success. Highlighting strategies to enhance participation, interaction, and focus, the research promotes more effective, supportive learning environments that can foster greater educational outcomes and social mobility for underserved populations.

Informed Consent and Assent.

In this study, all participating teachers will be required to provide informed consent and assent to ensure that ethical standards are upheld and their rights are safeguarded. Prior to participation, they will receive comprehensive information regarding the study's objectives, their expected involvement, data collection procedures, and any potential risks or benefits. Participation will be strictly voluntary, with the option to withdraw at any point without penalty. The informed consent form will detail confidentiality protocols, assuring participants that their responses will remain anonymous and used exclusively for research purposes. Assent will also be obtained to confirm their informed and voluntary agreement to participate.

Vulnerability of Research Respondents

The vulnerability of the research respondents, in this case, teachers, is an important consideration in this study. Teachers may experience vulnerability due to their professional roles, as they may feel pressure to provide re-

sponses that align with expectations or fear repercussions if their participation or feedback is perceived negatively. To address this, the study ensures confidentiality and emphasizes that participation is voluntary, with the option to withdraw at any time without any impact on their professional standing. This approach helps minimize any potential risks associated with vulnerability, ensuring that teachers can participate in the study without fear of judgment or consequences.

Privacy and Confidentiality

In this study, privacy and confidentiality are paramount to protect the personal information and responses of the teacher participants. All data collected will be kept anonymous, with no identifying information linked to the responses, ensuring that teachers' identities remain confidential. Any personal details shared during the study will be stored securely, accessible only to the research team, and used solely for research purposes. By maintaining strict confidentiality and respecting privacy, the study aims to create a safe environment where teachers can provide honest and unreserved feedback.

Risk, Benefits and Safety.

The risks associated with this study for the teacher participants are minimal. The primary risk involves the potential for discomfort when discussing personal views or experiences related to teaching practices and learner engagement, especially if the feedback is critical. However, confidentiality measures are in place to ensure anonymity, reducing any concerns about negative repercussions. The benefits of the study include contributing valuable insights into how alternative delivery modes (ADM) impact teacher engagement and teaching strategies, which may lead to more effective educational practices and support for teachers in their professional development. In terms of safety, the study will adhere to ethical guidelines, ensuring that all interactions are respectful and that participants are not exposed to any physical or emotional harm.

Justice

The justice of this study ensures that all teacher participants are treated fairly and equitably throughout the research process. Teachers from diverse backgrounds and teaching environments will be included, ensuring that their perspectives are represented and that no group is unfairly excluded. The study will also guarantee voluntary participation, and all teachers have the same opportunity to contribute regardless of their role or location. Furthermore, the study's findings will be shared to benefit all participants, providing insights that could improve teaching practices and inform policy without exploiting or favoring any individual or group. By adhering to fairness and equal treatment principles, the study aims to contribute positively to the educational community while respecting the rights and contributions of all involved.

Transparency

This study's transparency guarantees that teacher participants are well-informed about the research process, its goals, and the usage of their data. Every element of the study, such as its purpose, data collection methods, possible outcomes, and confidentiality safeguards, will be clearly conveyed to participants prior to their consent. Teachers will receive comprehensive details regarding their involvement in the study, the anticipated time commitment, and the voluntary aspect of their participation. Additionally, the results of the study will be shared with participants in a clear and accessible manner, ensuring that they can see how their input has contributed to the research findings. By maintaining openness throughout the study, transparency fosters trust and ensures that participants feel respected and informed.

Qualification of the Researcher

The qualifications of the researcher involved in this study are essential to ensure the credibility and integrity of the research process. The researcher possesses the requisite academic background, including expertise in educational

research, pedagogy, and learner engagement, with particular emphasis on alternative delivery modes (ADM). Moreover, the researcher has substantial experience in conducting mixed-methods studies, thereby ensuring a rigorous approach to data collection and analysis. Ethical research practices, encompassing the acquisition of informed consent and the maintenance of confidentiality, are fundamental to the researcher's methodology. Furthermore, the researcher is committed to respecting the perspectives and professional experience of the teacher participants, ensuring that their contributions are valued and used responsibly to inform the study's findings.

Conflict of Interest

In this study, efforts will be made to ensure there are no conflicts of interest that could bias the research process or the interpretation of findings. The teacher participants will be selected in a way that avoids any personal or professional relationships between the researcher and the respondents that could influence their responses or participation. The researcher has no financial or personal interests that would affect the study's outcome, and all findings will be presented objectively, based solely on the data collected. To maintain integrity, participants will be informed of the study's purpose and the researcher's neutrality, ensuring transparency and fairness throughout the research process.

Adequacy of Facilities

The adequacy of facilities for this study ensures that all necessary resources are available to conduct research effectively and ethically. The study will be conducted using accessible digital platforms for surveys and interviews, providing a convenient and secure environment for teacher participants to engage with the study. The researcher will ensure that the technology used for data collection is reliable and user-friendly, minimizing any barriers to participation. Appropriate data storage and analysis tools will also be utilized to maintain confidential-

ity and accuracy throughout the research process. With these facilities in place, the study is equipped to collect high-quality data and ensure a smooth and efficient research experience for all involved.

Community Involvement

The community involvement of this study is centered around engaging teacher participants as active contributors to the research process, ensuring that their voices are heard and valued. Teachers, as essential members of the educational community, will provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of alternative delivery modes (ADM) and their impact on learner engagement. The study encourages a collaborative method to grasp the challenges and opportunities in ADM by including teachers from various schools and backgrounds. Furthermore, it aspires to benefit the wider educational community by producing findings that can guide future teaching practices, policy decisions, and professional development programs. Through this collaborative process, the research empowers teachers to influence educational practices that directly affect their students and teaching environments.

2.3. Research Respondents—In the quantitative phase, the respondents were teachers from the General Roxas District who are directly involved in handling alternative delivery modes. These educators have direct experience with these modalities, making them ideal for offering insights into how these activities affect learner engagement. The district has a total of approximately 216 teachers, from which a sample size of 141 teachers has been determined. This sample size, representing a 95% confidence interval, was determined through a power analysis. In the quantitative data collection phase, the sample respondents' inclusion criteria were designed to ensure that participants are relevant to the study's objectives and can provide meaningful data on the relationship between alternative delivery modes (ADM) and learner engagement. The sample consisted of teachers who are currently involved

in the delivery of online, blended, or modular learning in educational settings. Teachers selected for inclusion needed to have at least one semester of experience using these alternative delivery modes in their classrooms, as this ensures they have sufficient experience to accurately assess and reflect on their students' engagement in these learning environments. Additionally, participants were willing to participate in the survey and provide honest, reflective feedback regarding the effectiveness of ADM in promoting learner engagement. Teachers from different grade levels and subject areas will be included to ensure a diverse range of perspectives, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis of ADM's impact across varying educational contexts. For the qualitative phase, eight participants were selected from the pool of teachers who participated in the quantitative phase. These participants will be purposefully chosen to ensure diversity in terms of teaching experience, subject area, and the type of ADM employed in their classrooms. Including these eight teachers will enable an in-depth exploration of their lived experiences, challenges, and perceptions regarding the impact of ADM on learner engagement. The qualitative data will be collected through interviews and classroom observations, enabling the researcher to gather rich, detailed insights into how different ADMs influence student participation, interaction, and focus. By selecting a small, diverse group of teachers for the qualitative phase, the study will ensure a variety of perspectives on the nuances of learner engagement within different alternative learning environments.

2.4. Research Instrument—In the quantitative phase of the study, the research instruments were adopted from Hermosisima, Mary Chandra R.; Mobo, Froilan D.; Cutillas, Anesito L. (2023) in their study, "Enhanced Learning Continuity Framework Using Online Teaching as Alternative Delivery Modality," and Juliet Aleta R. Villanueva; Petrea Redmond; Linda

Galligan; Douglas Eacersall (2024) in "Investigating Blended Learning Interactions in Philippine Schools through the Community of Inquiry Framework." These instruments will be subjected to content validity by a panel of experts, who will review them to ensure they accurately measure the intended constructs and are suitable for the study's context. The instruments underwent pilot testing with a small group of respondents from the target population to assess their reliability and validity. This process helped identify issues related to question clarity, measurement accuracy, and overall effectiveness. Based on the feedback, expert comments,

and suggested revisions, necessary modifications were made to finalize the instruments for the main data collection phase. The reliability of the instrument was confirmed with a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.885, indicating good internal consistency, as values above 0.80 are considered reliable and those above 0.90 are deemed excellent (Creswell, 2023). The questionnaire will use a 5-point Likert-type scale to determine the relationship between alternative delivery modes and learner engagement. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below;

Range of Mean and Descriptive Rating of Alternative Delivery Mode

Score	Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The implementation of alternative delivery mode/learner engagement is always observed and manifested.
4	3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The implementation of alternative delivery mode/learner engagement is oftentimes observed and manifested.
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The implementation of alternative delivery mode/learner engagement is sometimes observed and manifested.
2	1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The implementation of alternative delivery mode/learner engagement is seldom observed and manifested.
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The implementation of alternative delivery mode/learner engagement is never observed and manifested.

In the qualitative phase, the research instruments, specifically semi-structured interview guides, will be developed based on the frameworks provided by Hermosisima, Mary Chandra R.; Mobo, Froilan D.; Cutillas, Anesito L. (2023) and Juliet Aleta R. Villanueva; Petrea Redmond; Linda Galligan; Douglas Eacersall (2024). These instruments are tailored to ex-

plore the deeper, contextual factors influencing student leadership development and their engagement in school governance. The semi-structured interview format allows for flexible, open-ended questions, enabling participants to share detailed insights into their personal experiences with alternative delivery modes and learner engagement. As with the quantitative in-

struments, the qualitative tools will be reviewed by a panel of experts to ensure content validity and appropriateness for capturing rich, relevant data. After expert review, the instruments will undergo pilot testing with a smaller sample of a subset of the six participants selected for the qualitative phase. This testing will help refine the interview questions, clarify wording, and en-

sure that the instruments effectively elicit meaningful, reflective responses. Expert feedback will be carefully considered, and any suggested revisions or corrections will be incorporated into the final version of the interview guides. This process ensures the reliability and validity of qualitative data collection, enhancing the study's credibility and accuracy.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—The guidelines for the quantitative gathering procedure adhere to the policies of The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc. As part of the formal request, researchers delineate their intentions regarding data collection, analysis, and dissemination, aligning these with the overarching research goals. Anticipated concerns or questions from recipients are proactively addressed in this communication, providing assurances on ethical safeguards, confidentiality measures, and the potential benefits of the study. The formal permission request explicitly seeks authorization to proceed, emphasizing the pivotal role of their support in ensuring the research's success.

Permission to Conduct the Study

In February 2025, prior to data collection, the researcher secured the necessary permissions from relevant authorities, including the research adviser, the Dean of The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., and top management, through appropriate channels. This process entailed submitting a comprehensive research proposal that outlined the study design, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. The researcher also provided detailed information regarding the study's purpose, goals, and methods for data collection, analysis, and reporting. Additionally, in December 2024, right after the colloquium, the researcher made certain that all participants were completely aware of the study, their rights, and the details of their participation. Informed consent was secured before they took part in the research. During the last week of March 2025,

the researcher committed to data accuracy and completeness. The distribution and retrieval of questionnaires were conducted using a standardized and systematic approach, ensuring the reliability of the responses collected from participants.

Collation and statistical Treatment of Data

The researcher took time in data management. She ensured that accurate data gathered were sorted accordingly through Microsoft Excel and later transferred to JASP. All necessary information was collected. Consistency was also considered to make it relevant to the problem's statement. Reliability and validity were reviewed to lessen the degree of error in the analysis. During the qualitative phase of the study, data will be collected through semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions, and classroom observations to gain in-depth insights from eight selected teacher participants. These teachers will have already taken part in the quantitative phase, which means they are acquainted with the study's emphasis on alternative delivery modes (ADM) and learner engagement. The Semi-structured interviews will be conducted individually with each teacher, allowing for open-ended conversations where participants can share their personal experiences and reflections on how ADM influences learner engagement in their classrooms. A set of predetermined questions will guide the interviews focused on key themes of participation, interaction, and focus in ADM environments, but will also allow flexibility to explore emerging

topics or concerns raised by the participants. Focus group discussions will be organized to encourage group interaction and the sharing of ideas among teachers who have similar experiences with ADM. This method will provide participants an opportunity to discuss common challenges, strategies, and best practices for engaging learners in online, blended, or modular learning environments. The researcher will facilitate the focus groups to ensure that discussions remain focused on the study's themes while also allowing space for participants to offer their unique perspectives. Classroom observations will occur in teachers' actual settings, either in person or virtually, based on the delivery mode used teacher. These observations will focus on how teachers implement ADM and how students engage with these methods. The researcher will observe specific interactions, participation levels, and overall dynamics in the classroom, paying close attention to engagement indicators (participation, interaction, and focus) in real-time. All data gathered during the qualitative phase will be analyzed using thematic analysis, which involves identifying and interpreting recurring themes and patterns related to learner engagement in ADM environments. The goal is to generate a rich, detailed understanding of the factors that influence engagement from teachers' perspectives, providing a more

Trustworthiness of the Study

It is crucial to ensure this study's trustworthiness to confirm its results' accuracy, reliability, and validity. To achieve this trustworthiness, the research will prioritize four main criteria: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. These principles will guide the entire research process, ensuring that the data represents participants' experiences, that the findings apply in similar contexts, and that the study's procedures are consistent and transparent.

Credibility

This refers to the accuracy and credibility of the findings, ensuring that the data genuinely reflect the participants' perspectives and experiences. To enhance credibility, the study will employ multiple data collection methods (semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions, and classroom observations) to gather rich, detailed insights from teachers about their experiences with alternative delivery modes (ADM) and learner engagement. Additionally, member checking will be used, allowing participants the opportunity to review and validate their responses to ensure that their views are accurately captured. This process strengthens the study's internal validity by confirming that the findings align with the participants' lived experiences.

Transferability.

Refers to how the study's findings can be applied to various contexts or populations. Although the research focuses on a specific group of teachers engaged in ADM, it will offer detailed descriptions of the research context, participants, and findings, enabling others to evaluate the relevance of the conclusions in different educational settings. Additionally, the study will provide rich, in-depth accounts of the participants' experiences, aiding future researchers in assessing the applicability of the findings to similar or diverse educational environments.

Dependability

Is concerned with the consistency and reliability of the study's findings over time. To ensure dependability, the study will maintain a clear and systematic data collection process, including well-defined procedures for interviews, focus groups, and observations. Detailed documentation of each step of the research process will be kept, including any changes or challenges encountered, which will allow the findings to be tracked and understood in context. The researcher will also ensure that the process is transparent and that the methodology is consistent across participants, enabling others to replicate the study if needed.

Confirmability

. Refers to the objectivity and neutrality of the researcher in interpreting the data. To enhance confirmability, the researcher will actively engage in reflexivity, being aware of and transparent about any personal biases or preconceptions that could influence the interpretation of the data. The researcher will also maintain an

audit trail, documenting all decisions made during the study, from data collection to analysis, ensuring that the results derive from the perspectives of the participants, not the researcher's personal views biases. This audit trail established that the conclusions drawn are grounded in the data rather than influenced by researcher bias.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The subsequent statistical tools were employed to analyze the correlation between alternative delivery modes and learner engagement. The mean score and descriptive interpretations were used to answer statement problems 1 and 2 regarding the extent of implementation of the alternative delivery mode and learner engagement. Pearson r or Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer statement problem number 3 about the significant relationship between implementing an alternative delivery mode and learner engagement. Simple Linear Regression Analysis was used to answer statement problem number 4 on the significant influence of alternative delivery mode towards learner engagement. In the qualitative phase of the study, the analyses of problems 5 and 6 will be conducted utilizing thematic analysis, a widely recognized method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (or themes) within qualitative data. The analysis commenced with data familiarization, wherein the researcher engaged in an extensive review of the transcribed interviews to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the content. Subsequently, initial coding was performed, which entails the identification of significant features within the data, such as keywords, phrases, or ideas, and the assignment of labels (codes) to them. These codes were then organized into broader themes that encapsulate the essential aspects of the data pertinent to the research questions (Creswell, J.W. and Creswell J. D., 2023). Once the ini-

tial coding is complete, the researcher developed themes, organizing the codes into coherent themes that represent the underlying patterns across the data. This process involved reviewing the coded data and refining the themes to ensure they reflect the key findings of leadership development and governance engagement. The researcher used peer debriefing and member checking to ensure the themes are credible and reflect participants' true experiences (Creswell, J.W. and Creswell J. D., 2023). Ultimately, the identified themes were examined within the study's theoretical framework and research questions. This examination enabled the researcher to derive valuable conclusions regarding the Relationship Between alternative delivery modes and learner engagement. This approach yielded a comprehensive understanding of participants' views, ensuring that the analysis is data-driven while revealing significant insights into the study's larger implications (Creswell, J.W. and Creswell J. D., 2023).

Sequence, Emphasis and Mixing Procedures

Sequence. The study follows an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design, which begins with the quantitative phase followed by the qualitative phase. In the quantitative phase, a survey was administered to gather data on learner engagement in different alternative delivery modes (ADM), focusing on variables such as participation, interaction, and focus. This initial phase aims to identify general patterns and relationships between ADM and learner engagement. Once the quantitative data is analyzed, the quali-

tative phase follows, where in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and classroom observations were conducted with a selected group of teachers. The qualitative phase aims to provide deeper insights into the findings from the quantitative phase, offering a richer understanding of the factors that influence learner engagement in ADM environments.

Emphasis. The quantitative phase emphasizes collecting numerical data to identify broad trends and correlations between ADM and learner engagement. Statistical analysis, such as correlational analysis, were used to quantify the relationship between variables, providing an overview of how ADM affect participation, interaction, and focus. The qualitative phase, on the other hand, emphasizes understanding the participants' lived experiences. In-depth interviews and observations will focus on capturing the nuances and personal perspectives of teachers, shedding light on the contextual factors and teaching strategies that foster or hinder learner engagement in ADM settings. While the

quantitative phase provides breadth, the qualitative phase adds depth to the findings, highlighting the complexities of engagement in different learning environments.

Mixing Procedures. Quantitative and qualitative data integration occurred at two key stages. First, in the data analysis phase, the quantitative results from the survey will be used to identify key patterns and correlations, which then inform the design of the qualitative data collection tools (such as interview guides and observation protocols). The qualitative findings were used to interpret and explain the quantitative results, providing a more detailed understanding of the mechanisms behind the patterns observed. Second, in the interpretation phase, both sets of data were merged to offer a comprehensive view of how ADM impacts learner engagement. The quantitative data highlighted broad trends and relationships, while the qualitative data will provide context, explaining why and how certain ADM influence engagement in specific ways.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results of both the quantitative and qualitative phases, following an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design. Survey data were first analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics to address the research questions and examine variable relationships. Qualitative data from interviews were then thematically analyzed to contextualize and enrich the quantitative findings. The integration of both data sets provides a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon, aligning statistical results with participants' lived experiences.

3.1. Extent of Alternative Delivery Mode Implementation—Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) refers to the innovative, non-traditional education strategies employed to provide access to quality basic education for learners who are unable to participate in the conventional classroom setting due to geographic, economic, cultural, or social barriers. As mandated by the Department of Education (DepEd), ADM seeks to uphold the right to inclusive and equitable education by offering various flexible learning

options tailored to the learners' contexts (DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2019). ADM implementation involves the deployment of specially designed instructional materials, modular learning packages, and flexible teaching modalities that cater to the diverse needs of marginalized learners, including those in remote communities, working students, indigenous peoples, and learners-at-risk. Common forms of ADM include Modular Distance Learning, Home-Based Learning, Electronic Learning, Radio-Based Instruc-

tion, and the Modified In-School Off-School Approach (MISOSA), among others. The effectiveness of ADM implementation depends on several key dimensions: curriculum alignment and contextualization, teacher preparedness and adaptability, availability of learning resources, frequency and quality of teacher-learner interactions, and parental or community involvement. Moreover, ADM requires strategic monitoring and support mechanisms to ensure that learning competencies are achieved despite the limitations of face-to-face instruction. Research underscores the relevance of ADM in bridging educational gaps. For instance, Delos Santos and Javier (2022) emphasized that the implementation of ADM during the COVID-19 pandemic ensured learning continuity, though it also revealed challenges such as limited access to technology and increased parental responsibility. Likewise, the study of Garcia and Magno (2021) highlighted that ADM can promote learner autonomy and engagement if instructional designs are responsive and culturally relevant. Summary of the Extent of Alternative Delivery Mode Implementation

Table 1 outlines the learners’ perspectives

on the extent of implementation of various alternative delivery modes. All modes—online learning (M = 2.74), blended learning (M = 2.94), modular learning (M = 3.24), face-to-face learning (M = 3.64), and hybrid learning (M = 2.69)—were perceived as Moderately Extensive, with a cumulative mean of 3.14. Among the delivery types, face-to-face learning received the highest mean, suggesting that it remains the most effectively and extensively implemented modality. In contrast, hybrid learning scored the lowest (M = 2.69), revealing ongoing challenges in integrating digital and in-person components. These findings are consistent with recent literature. According to Palese et al. (2023), traditional face-to-face modalities remain the most preferred and smoothly executed form of delivery, especially in developing educational systems, due to existing infrastructure and familiarity. However, modular learning has also gained traction in remote and under-resourced contexts. A study by Camacho-Zuñiga et al. (2021) observed that printed modular materials are perceived as highly accessible and dependable, particularly where internet connectivity remains inconsistent.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Alternative Delivery Mode Implementation

No	Alternative Delivery Mode Implementation	n	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Online learning	141	2.74	Moderately Extensive
2	Blended learning	141	2.94	Moderately Extensive
3	Modular learning	141	3.24	Moderately Extensive
4	Face-to-face learning	141	3.64	Moderately Extensive
5	Hybrid learning	141	2.69	Moderately Extensive
Mean Average		141	3.14	Moderately Extensive

Blended and online learning models, though promising, remain moderately adopted due to pedagogical and technical gaps. Ramadani et al. (2022) noted that while online platforms ex-

panded access during pandemic-related disruptions, their effectiveness depends on students’ digital literacy, reliable internet access, and instructors’ adaptive teaching strategies. Simi-

larly, Perveen and Asif (2024) highlighted that blended learning environments require deliberate instructional planning and support systems to reach full efficacy. The consistently moderate scores across modalities, especially for hybrid and online learning, echo the findings of Lasekan et al. (2022), who argue that alternative delivery modes are only as successful as their contextual adaptation. Without adequate teacher training, learner support, and resource provision, such modes remain underutilized despite their theoretical benefits.

3.2. Extent of Learner Engagement Given the Implementation—Learner engagement refers to the degree of attention, interest, curiosity, and emotional investment that students exhibit during the learning process. It is a multidimensional construct that significantly contributes to academic achievement, motivation, and long-term educational success (Fredricks, Blumenfeld, Paris, 2004). In contemporary educational discourse, learner engagement is often categorized into three interrelated dimensions: behavioral, emotional, and cognitive engagement. Behavioral engagement involves students' participation in academic, social, and extracurricular activities. It is reflected in attendance, task completion, active participation, and compliance with school norms (Appleton et al., 2006). Emotional engagement, on the other hand, refers to students' affective reactions in the classroom, including interest, enjoyment, a sense of belonging, and attachment to teachers and peers. Cognitive engagement includes the willingness and effort to invest in learning, the use of deep learning strategies, and self-regulated learning behaviors (Reeve, 2012). Learner engagement is a critical determinant of academic outcomes across various delivery modes. In face-to-face learning environments, engagement is often facilitated through direct teacher-student interactions and

collaborative activities. In alternative delivery modalities such as online, modular, or blended learning, maintaining learner engagement poses unique challenges due to reduced immediacy and limited social interaction (Bond et al., 2021). Empirical studies emphasize the importance of designing instruction that promotes active, meaningful participation. For example, Martin and Bolliger (2022) found that student engagement in online settings increased significantly when instructors employed interactive tools, frequent feedback, and synchronous communication. Meanwhile, Pascual and Padilla (2023) underscored the need for differentiated strategies to sustain engagement in modular learning, especially among learners in marginalized and remote contexts. In sum, learner engagement is a dynamic and essential component of the teaching and learning process. Whether in traditional or alternative delivery modes, its enhancement depends on the alignment of instructional design, learner needs, and contextual responsiveness. Summary of the Extent of Learner Engagement Given the Implementation

Table 2 summarizes the extent of learner engagement under alternative delivery mode implementation across four core dimensions: participation, interaction, focus, and collaboration. The overall mean score of 2.80 indicates that learner engagement is Moderately Extensive. Among the dimensions, collaboration ($M = 3.09$) and focus ($M = 3.06$) received higher ratings, suggesting that learners are relatively more engaged in group-related tasks and maintain a reasonable level of concentration during learning. However, the dimensions of participation and interaction both received a mean of 2.54, interpreted as Less Extensive, indicating that learners are not consistently active or communicative during sessions conducted through alternative delivery modalities.

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Learner Engagement Given the Implementation

No	Learner Engagement	n	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Participation	141	2.54	Less Extensive
2	Interaction	141	2.54	Less Extensive
3	Focus	141	3.06	Moderately Extensive
4	Collaboration	141	3.09	Moderately Extensive
Mean Average		141	2.80	Moderately Extensive

These findings are in line with recent research. Murphy et al. (2022) found that while students may retain attention during self-paced or modular learning, active participation and peer-to-peer interaction often decline without structured teacher facilitation. This aligns with the lower engagement ratings in participation and interaction. Similarly, Pérez-Juárez et al. (2024) highlighted that digital distractions, lack of immediacy, and cognitive overload in online platforms contribute to passive learner behavior and reduced communicative exchanges. In contrast, Xu et al. (2023) demonstrated that when collaborative mechanisms and visual peer cues are embedded in virtual learning environments, learners tend to show greater focus and engagement. Vraga et al. (2023) also reported that learner collaboration and cognitive presence are enhanced when structured group activities are integrated into hybrid settings, thereby explaining the moderate scores in collaboration and focus. Overall, the findings underscore the partial success of alternative delivery modes in fostering learner engagement. While learners are able to concentrate and collaborate to a moderate extent, the implementation still falls short in promoting consistent participation and interactive learning. To address these gaps, educational planners should emphasize synchronous sessions, peer-led activities, and interactive tools that reinforce communicative and participatory behaviors in digital and blended learning envi-

ronments.

3.3. Relationship Between Alternative Delivery Mode Implementation And Learner Engagement—Table 3 presents the statistical analysis of the relationship between Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) Implementation and Learner Engagement using Pearson’s correlation. The computed r-value of 0.153 with a p-value of 0.071 indicates a very weak positive correlation that is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level of confidence. Thus, the result leads to the decision to accept the null hypothesis (H) and reject the alternative hypothesis (H).

Since the p-value exceeds the critical threshold ($p = .071 > .05$), the study fails to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that the degree to which ADM is implemented does not have a statistically significant association with how engaged learners are, at least within the scope and context of this study. These findings align with the observations of Bond et al. (2021), who argued that while ADM may expand access to education, it does not inherently guarantee increased engagement unless accompanied by structured support, interactive strategies, and teacher facilitation. Similarly, Pascual and Padilla (2023) found that even well-implemented ADM strategies such as modular and online learning often result in disengagement due to lack of real-time interaction, delayed feedback, and insufficient monitoring

mechanisms. It may be inferred that other mediating factors such as learner motivation, parental support, digital access, and instructional quality could significantly influence engagement out-

comes more than ADM implementation alone. Thus, while ADM is a necessary response to educational disruptions, its effect on engagement remains conditional and context-driven.

Table 3. Relationship between Alternative Delivery Mode Implementation and Learner Engagement

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Alternative Delivery Mode Implementation	0.153	0.071	Not Significant	Accept H0

*significant at $p < 0.05$.

3.4. Alternative Delivery Modes Significantly Influence Learner Engagement—The non-significant p-value further supports the conclusion that the combination of ADM strategies included in this study does not significantly predict the level of learner engagement. These findings are consistent with the observations of Garcia and Roque (2021), who argued that the effectiveness of ADM modalities may depend more on how they are implemented, especially in terms of interaction, assessment, and learner support than on the modality itself.

All p-values exceed the 0.05 significance level, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis for each ADM predictor; none of the delivery modes significantly influence learner engagement when considered individually. These findings highlight that while ADM approaches are critical for access and continuity, they alone do not predict engagement levels, echoing the conclusions of Calimag and Del Rosario (2022) and Martin and Bolliger

(2022), who emphasized that instructional design, teacher feedback, and learner support systems are the primary enablers of engagement in remote or hybrid contexts. Furthermore, Domingo and Silva (2023) noted that even within effective modular programs, engagement depends heavily on the availability of teacher feedback, community support, and learners’ self-regulation skills—factors not captured directly by modality type. The regression analysis indicates that while Alternative Delivery Modes are necessary for educational continuity, they are not sufficient predictors of learner engagement. Their effectiveness likely depends on the quality of implementation, instructional interaction, and contextual factors such as learners’ digital readiness, home environment, and school support systems. Future research should consider these variables as moderators or mediators to better understand the complex relationship between delivery modes and student engagement.

3.5. Standpoints Of the Participants Regarding the Extent Of Alternative Delivery Mode Implementation and Learner Engagement—The qualitative findings substantively reinforce the quantitative results presented earlier in the study. Quantitative data showed that ADM

implementation was moderately extensive, but learner engagement, particularly in participation and interaction, was rated less extensive. The non-significant correlation between ADM implementation and learner engagement ($r = 0.153$, $p = .071$) further underscores the qualitative in-

Table 4. Adaptation Strategies that Significantly Influence Learning Outcomes

Model	Parameter	Unstanardized	Standard Error	Standardized	t	p	Decision
M ₀	(Intercept)	2.804	0.033		85.530	<.001	
M ₁	(Intercept)	2.372	0.288		8.247	<.001	
	OL_AVE	0.052	0.052	0.102	1.009	0.315	Accept Null
	BL_AVE	0.018	0.064	0.029	0.283	0.777	Accept Null
	ML_AVE	0.087	0.060	0.140	1.447	0.150	Accept Null
	FFL_AVE	0.034	0.062	0.049	0.558	0.578	Accept Null
	HL_AVE	-0.064	0.063	-0.093	-1.008	0.315	Accept Null

sight that delivery modality alone does not determine engagement outcomes. Rather, it is the quality of implementation, contextual responsiveness, and the presence of supportive structures (e.g., feedback mechanisms, parental and teacher support, interactive strategies) that ultimately shape the learner’s experience. The con-

vergence of qualitative and quantitative findings is a hallmark of explanatory sequential mixed-methods research. In this study, the qualitative phase provides explanatory depth and contextual texture to the numeric trends, revealing the underlying mechanisms behind the statistical patterns observed.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the conclusions derived from the findings of the study, guided by the specific statements of the problem. It also offers recommendations anchored on the results of both quantitative and qualitative analyses to inform policy, instructional practices, and future research directions. The conclusions summarize the essential insights on the extent of Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) implementation and its relationship to learner engagement, while the recommendations provide actionable strategies to enhance ADM practices and foster meaningful learner participation across various educational settings.

4.1. Findings—The extent of implementation of Alternative Delivery Modes (ADM) and the corresponding level of learner engagement were found to be moderately extensive overall. Among the four modes, face-to-face learning had the highest implementation rating (M = 3.64), followed by modular learning (M = 3.24), blended learning (M = 2.94), hybrid learning (M=2.69) and online learning (M = 2.74). In terms of engagement, collaboration (M = 3.09), focus was moderately extensive (M = 3.06), while participation and interaction were both rated less extensive (M = 2.54), indi-

cating engagement gaps across ADM formats. The relationship between ADM implementation and learner engagement was found to be not statistically significant (r = 0.153, p = 0.071), leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. ADM alone does not predict learner engagement. Regression analysis confirmed that none of the ADM types significantly influenced engagement, with all predictors showing p-values above 0.05. Qualitative data revealed that participants viewed ADM as flexible but limited, with learner engagement highly dependent on contextual factors such as technology access, home

environment, and instructional quality. Participants believed there is a perceived link between ADM and engagement, particularly when supported by strong teacher-student interaction and well-structured learning activities.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn: The implementation of Alternative Delivery Modes (ADM)—including online, blended, modular, and face-to-face learning—is generally moderately extensive, with face-to-face and modular modes perceived as the most effectively implemented. Learner engagement remains inconsistent across modalities. While learners exhibit moderate levels of focus, their participation and interaction are considerably less extensive, suggesting that access to ADM does not necessarily equate to active engagement. The statistical analysis revealed no significant relationship between ADM implementation and learner engagement, implying that the use of alternative modalities alone is not a strong predictor of how engaged learners will be. Furthermore, no specific ADM type significantly influenced learner engagement, indicating that other variables—such as instructional quality, learner motivation, and teacher support—play a more critical role. Participants perceive ADM as a flexible and essential approach, especially in times of disruption. However, they emphasized that teacher-student interaction, contextual adaptation, and instructional responsiveness are crucial mediating factors for sustaining learner engagement.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed: Strengthen teacher capacity in ADM facilitation. Professional development programs should focus on enhancing teachers' skills in designing interactive, engaging, and learner-centered activities within all delivery modes. Invest In Supportive Infrastructure. Schools and divisions must ensure reliable access to digital tools, internet connectivity, and

learning resources, especially in underserved areas, to address technological barriers that hinder engagement.

For Parents. The study highlights how alternative delivery modes impact their children's learning experiences and engagement. This can empower parents to provide better support for their children's learning, monitor engagement levels, and collaborate more effectively with teachers to ensure their child's academic success, particularly in non-traditional learning settings. **For the School Principal.** The study provides valuable data to public school district supervisors, helping them evaluate the efficacy of alternative delivery modes across various schools in the district. It can assist in making district-level decisions regarding training for teachers, resource distribution, and strategies to increase student engagement and success in diverse learning environments. **For the Public School District Supervisor.** District supervisors will find this study significant as it provides data on the positive impact of extracurricular activities, such as Girl Scout programs, on student engagement in school governance. The study can inform district-wide policies and initiatives aimed at promoting student leadership and participation in school activities. It can also serve as a basis for advocating for more support and resources for extracurricular programs that contribute to student development. **For DepEd Officials.** The research findings can provide Department of Education (DepEd) officials with evidence to assist in creating policies that enhance and diversify educational delivery. This study will aid in evidence-based decision-making for adopting alternative learning methods, developing professional programs for teachers, and distributing resources to boost student engagement across the country. **For Future Researchers.** Future researchers can build on this study's findings by exploring related topics, such as the long-term effects of alternative delivery modes on student achievement, the

role of technology in learning, or the broader socio-economic implications of these teaching methods. This study will provide a foundational framework for further investigating effective teaching practices and engagement strategies in diverse educational settings. Prioritize Instructional Interaction

Regardless of modality, regular teacher-learner communication, feedback mechanisms, and academic monitoring should be institutionalized to promote active engagement and accountability. Customize ADM strategies based

on learner context Schools should adopt flexible and differentiated approaches that reflect the specific needs, learning styles, and environments of their students to maximize engagement outcomes.

Conduct Further Research on Mediating Variables Future studies should explore factors such as teacher presence, family involvement, learner autonomy, and emotional well-being as possible determinants of engagement in ADM contexts.

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